

**KHALED HOSSEINI'S ROLE IN AMERICAN LITERATURE AS A EXEMPLARY
OF IMMIGRANT GENRE AND HIS BESTSELLERS**

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Abstract:

In this article, the authors analyze the key aspects of the Khaled Hosseini's works and his contribution to the American literature. The authors explore the style and genre of the famous books of Khaled Hosseini. They delve into the aspects of immigrant genre, its difference from other genres and compare it to other American authors works.

Key words: literature, genres, American literature, Khaled Hosseini, immigrant genre

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Introduction. Khaled Hosseini is an internationally acclaimed novelist, philanthropist, a former doctor, a refugee, an American Citizen, and an Afghani. Khaled Hosseini is known for his best-selling novels and his philanthropic contributions as a Goodwill Ambassador for the UNHCR and the founder of the Khaled Hosseini Foundation. Khaled Hosseini is important in English literature because his novels have presented life in Afghanistan to a global audience, subtly weaving insights into Afghanistan's complex religious, social, and political history into his engaging character-driven narratives.

This novelist is also important to English literature because of the caliber of his writing. His works of fiction, widely read and studied throughout the world, belong to the canon of Seminal World Literature. Khaled Hosseini's writing style is characterized by tenderness and empathy. It is deeply personal and highly descriptive. He investigates every facet of his character's emotions and doesn't shy away from depicting deeply intimate actions, such as rape, childbirth, grief, and suicide. In doing so he gets to the core of each character and their motives. Even the villains, such as Rasheed in *A Thousand Splendid Suns* (2007), are shown as complex, fully-rounded characters. The reader is shown his guilt and grief at his first son's death and his raw love for his youngest son.

Discussing his other works it is possible to say that: he *Kite Runner* covers themes such as infidelity, familial bonds, sexual abuse, trust and betrayal, atonement, and racism. The novel explains the different ethnic groups in Afghanistan, and the racism faced by members of the Hazara ethnic minority group.

A Thousand Splendid Suns cover themes such as misogyny, domestic violence, infertility, sacrifice, and love. Its most prominent theme is that of parenthood. Khaled

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Hosseini's exploration of this theme is multifaceted, exploring child-loss and infertility as well as parenthood. He presents his readers with an array of different types of parents: loving, neglectful, dedicated, grieving, and selfish.

Results and its discussion. The Kite Runner covers themes such as infidelity, familial bonds, sexual abuse, trust and betrayal, atonement, and racism. The novel explains the different ethnic groups in Afghanistan, and the racism faced by members of the Hazara ethnic minority group.

A Thousand Splendid Suns cover themes such as misogyny, domestic violence, infertility, sacrifice, and love. Its most prominent theme is that of parenthood. Khaled Hosseini's exploration of this theme is multifaceted, exploring child-loss and infertility as well as parenthood. He presents his readers with an array of different types of parents: loving, neglectful, dedicated, grieving, and selfish.

H. Hosseini's novels belong to the genre of the so-called "immigration novel" because the author is not only an immigrant, but also touches on topics such as life in Afghanistan, the Afghan community in the United States and its adaptation difficulties to new cultural conditions. The analyzed works are united artistic chronotype – Afghanistan at the end of the 20th – beginning of the 21st century, time of change regimes, wars and destruction, on the one hand, and the modern USA and Europe, Afghan immigrant communities, on the other hand. In all novels, the author's concept of the homeland is realized, although it is not basic.

Khaled Hosseini, who immigrated to the United States at age 11, is an exponent of translanguaging. Translanguaging is interpreted as a type of bilingualism (bilingualism) as "a smooth synergetic transition from one linguistic culture to another, as a result of which some merging occurs, without their complete assimilation and preserves the linguacultural identity of language users, and also creates mixed discourse".

Texts created by translanguaging are characterized by linguacultural heterogeneity - the implementation in the text of the interaction of at least two cultures. For Khaled Hosseini, the linguistic culture of Afghanistan remains the basis of his work. However, in his English-language works are dominated by Western traditions, because by the time Hosseini's writing has long adapted to a culture that is secondary to him. Nevertheless, he "acts as a translator of Afghan culture, which for him is a mixture of Afghan culture proper and the more ancient Persian, which had a very powerful influence on the first"

Conclusion. Hosseini's novels are marked by linguacultural heterogeneity, which corresponds to the main task of the writer - to act as a cultural intermediary between Afghan and Western cultures. The external pragmatics of titles is realized primarily by their intriguing function. The internal pragmatics of the titles corresponds to the general pragmatic strategy of the author - to convey to the reader information of a cultural nature and form emotional and evaluative meanings.

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